

National Identity of Adolescents: A Thematic Analysis

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Abstract

To explore the components and factors influencing the national identity of Pakistani adolescents, a thematic analysis approach was used to analyze the data. A conveniently approached, purposive sample comprised of nine adolescent boys and nine adolescent girls of age ranged between 15 and 17 years belonged to different cities of Pakistan. These adolescents were students of 9th-10th grades. Thematic analysis revealed that national identity comprised of two components (viz., belongingness, and a sense of nation). The analysis also revealed that salient factors were parents, teachers, economic conditions, media, and peer that influenced these components of national identity. Current study provides strong theoretical and practical implications for the national identity development of adolescents of Pakistan.

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Introduction

Identity is a system of thinking about oneself that develops during adolescence (Erikson, 1968). Adolescence is considered a critical period of all age groups. During adolescence, the child continues to grow physically, cognitively, and emotionally, changing from a child into an adult. The body grows rapidly in size and the sexual and reproductive organs become fully functional. At the same time, as adolescents develop more advanced patterns of reasoning and a stronger sense of self, they seek to construct their own identities, establishing key attachments with people other than their parents and establishing certain beliefs (Lam & Tam, 2011). The aspects of identity can all contribute to the development of different types of identities, such as national, religious, gender, cultural, and social class. Among these facets of identity, national identity is a kind of identity that plays significant role in the life plans, goals, priorities and life style of an individual. National identity is defined as a set of emotions and cognitions that expresses a relationship of an individual with a nation (Barrett & Davis 2008). National identity includes subjective conviction, positive or negative emotions toward a nation, strong sense of national affiliation, stereotypes related to traits and characteristics of individuals belonging either to other national group or their own national group, subjective opinions with regard to current aims and nation's problem, inclusiveness experience and perception of oneself as similar to other members of group with regard to important group defining characters, to follow the behavioral norms and willingness to internalize the values and national culture. National identity influence cognitions, affects and behavior of individuals (Barrett, 2005). Keeping in view the importance of national identity and salience of identity development in adolescence, current study was designed to explore adolescents' subjective sense of their national identity development during this developmental period.

Nationalism and patriotism are two interrelated concepts, which are well connected with the development of national identity, and would be underlying the formation of national identity (Greenfeld & Chiost, 1994; Hobsbawm, 2011; Leite, 2002). Nationalism functions as an ideological basis in forming national identity (Tinsley, 2014). It means that people perceive themselves as special figures as inhabitants of a nation (Hastings, 1999). It is difficult to define nationalism (Kunhavalik, 2009). However, it may be perceived as an ideological movement at the unity, autonomy, and identity of a population beyond a social movement, considering as a potential or real nation (Smith, 1991). In contrast to nationalism, patriotism is a sense of loyalty that is tied to the nation (Sewpaul, 2009). It is often used as synonymous with nationalism (Billig, 1995; Sewpaul, 2009). Yet, patriotism may involve the development of a sense of morality of duty, self-sacrifice, and self preservation (Acton, 1985). Patriotism is associated with love of country but it cannot be used as a substitute of nationalism. Patriotism is linked to a way of life that guarantees freedom, to love, and welfare of nation whereas nationalism refers to cultural and/or ethnic identity (Viroli, 1997).

Education, economic conditions, parents, peer group, and media are important factors that play a vital role in the formation of national identity. It is said that citizens should be educated that they must have a sense of nationhood for the better survival and successful future of their nation. The state cannot exercise authority over citizens until they are not agreed to make sacrifices for the betterment of the nation (e.g., serving in the army, paying taxes, etc.) by perceiving themselves to be members of a collective nation. Along with the media,

education system plays a vital role in the development of national identity. It creates behavioral norms, defining values, national goals, and national myths. However, the role of education has hardly been studied empirically in the formation of national identity (Eaton, 2002). The distinction has been made by the researchers between patriotic education and critical education. Patriotic education increases the respectful approach towards the country, national symbols, institutions, and authority figures (e.g., President, Prime Minister, the King). It also enhances the feelings of pride among students (Rapoport, 2009). Whereas critical education places the values of civil society and democracy over state by appraising the military history of the state and the military's present effect on the youth of the country. In critical education personal interests are more important than the interest of state (Rapoport, 2009). According to the supporters of patriotic as well as critical educationists claim that the purpose of their approaches is to enhance the sense of national identity among youth.

Socioeconomic conditions of any country play vital role in the national identity of individuals but this important area have not yet received proper attention from researchers. A study conducted on adolescents (15-18-year-old) revealed that the economic conditions of a country influence the national identity of adolescents (Poppe & Linssen 1999). Results of another study conducted on the sample of Russia and Ukraine adolescents of age ranged between 15 and 16-year old (Tartakovsky, 2010), revealed that level of affiliation with the country was found to be higher among adolescents of Russia as compared to the adolescents of Ukraine. The difference in scores were attributed to the better economic conditions of Russia (Legatum Institute, 2009). Poppe (2002), in nine European countries compared the competence stereotypes and economic conditions in 1994 and in 1995. An improvement in the attitude of adolescents was found toward their own countries which followed an improvement in economic condition in their countries whereas, no changes were found in perceived competence. In contrast, no change was found in the degree of identification with the nation in a study conducted by Tartakovsky (2010) in 1999–2007 in Russia and Ukraine.

The influence of parents is direct as well as contextual on the national identity of their children. Children learn from their parents how they should develop relations with other nations and with their own country. Emotionally colored information about their own and other nations are obtained by children from their parents. Expression of parents regarding their own and other nations are heard, memorized, and repeated by children. Parents also encourage the interactions of their children with the children of other national groups. In bilingual regions, children's use of language and selection of language that will be used at home and wherever possible is affected by parents (e.g., Reizabal et al., 2004; Bollen & Medrano, 1998). People living in countries having conflicts with neighbors are more conscious about the national identity of their children. Thus a study conducted by Muldoon et al. (2007a) in North Ireland indicated that Catholic parents infuse their own negative feelings in their children against Protestant British. Similar parental influence regarding the national identity of children was found in Cyprus (Philippou, 2005).

The parental effect on children's national identity is also contextual. Children build an internal representation (an internal working model) of their parents while developing an attachment to them (Mikulincer & Shaver, 2007). Children generalize this internal representation obtained by parents to relate with parents. A more positive internal working model of the respondents' mothers was found to be associated with a more positive attitude towards the country but not with a greater identification with the nation in a series of researches in Ukraine, Russia, and Israel (Walsh & Tartakovsky, 2012).

Adolescent's national identity may also be determined by peers either directly or contextually. The need for belongingness among adolescents is satisfied with good relations with peers that encourages them to form a positive attitude towards their country. Moreover, internal representation with peers may move onto the entire nation. In a recent study, positive attitude toward the country and strong identification with the nation among high school adolescents was found to be positively correlated with high quality peer relations (Tartakovsky, 2010). Moreover, high school adolescents having strong bonding with their peers were found to have a more positive attitude towards their country than those adolescents having insecure attachment with their peers (Tartakovsky, 2010).

Media plays a critical role in the creation and maintenance of national narrative and national identity (Carey, 1992). Through media consumption, a kind of group rituals similar to attending a mass is created that gives direction and a sense of fellowship. Discursive strategies of national identity construction are also utilized by media content. Media coverage is a reflection of the national identity of any nation because similar values and beliefs tend to be reflected by journalists as it is reproduced by the rest of the nation. Nationalist themes in crises having a perceived threat to national security or national interests are reflected by news coverage (Hutcheson et al., 2004, p. 31). Adolescents use all forms of media (Arnett, Larson, Offer, 1995) that play important role in providing information and cultural materials to young people with regard to occupations, gender roles, and political values which are involved in the formation of national identity (Arnett, 1995; Brown, Childers, & Waszak, 1990).

Uses and Gratification approach guides to know about the conduct and inspiration of people to understand the impact of the use of media (Rubin, 1993). According to McQuail (1984, 1987), there are four categories of media use by individuals: personal identity, integration and social interaction, information, and

entertainment. All these categories help adolescents in the development of their national identity (McQuail, 1984; Rubin, 1993). The term “national identification” was used by Blank, Schmidt, and Westle (2001) to explain the intensity of feeling towards one’s nation. They also used the term “nationalism” and “patriotism” for questions that are related to content and national identity. Pye (2004) described that the consumption of media and the formation of national identity are directly related because the stories that are told by journalists to their readers are created by linking the present with the past as emphasized by Le (2006).

In Pakistan, very few studies had been carried out on the phenomenon of national identity for example, Durrani (2008) established a relationship between gender and national identity formation. Results revealed that gender differences were reinforced by the education system. Keeping in view the importance of national identity, the current study designed to qualitatively explore the process of national identity development of adolescents in the context of Pakistan.

Method Sample

The purposive sample ($N=18$) constituted of middle adolescents (15- 17 years) was taken from all the provinces of Pakistan. Only Muslim students enrolled in the 9th and 10th grades were included in the study. There were eight boys and eight girls in the sample. The sample was selected to ensure homogeneity in various domains: the adolescents from intact families were selected and the adolescents living with single parents (divorced, separated and widow/widower) were not included in the study.

Instrument

A semi structured interview was used for data collection. After taking permission from Marcia, his interview protocol (Marcia, 1993) was used to devise the interview protocol for the current study. Interview protocol comprised of questions regarding the national identity of students (i.e., What type of feeling you experience about your country; How do you see your future in Pakistan). Fifteen open-ended questions were finalized with the help of a committee comprised of social scientists from different social science departments of the university.

Procedure

In order to collect the data, permission was taken from the parents. After the permission consent of participants was taken. Participants were briefed about the purpose of the study. Confidentiality and privacy of data were ensured. After taking permission, complete interviews were recorded through an audio recorder. The interview took average 35 minutes and participants showed great interest in the topic and they openly discussed their ideas without any hesitation.

Data Analysis

On the basis of Braun and Clarke (2006) guidelines, thematic analysis was used to analyze the data. The thematic analysis helped in the extraction of themes regarding the components, process and factoring influencing the development of national identity. Thematic analysis is considered as a flexible approach and it helps in determining the process and components of any phenomenon (Attride-Stirling, 2001, p. 387). It is considered as a best method to get meaningful and easily understandable themes (Braun & Clarke, 2006).

Based on Braun and Clarke (2006) instructions, firstly all interviews were completely transcribed. The Pseudonyms were used for the names of participants. Codes were generated and data were reduced. It was ensured that codes were the meaningful chunks. After rechecking the codes, themes were developed. The thematic map of themes was discussed with the experts and then the names of themes were decided. At the end, report was generated on the basis of themes.

The creditability of research was ensured through ensuring the control of personal bias and consensus of experts regarding the finalization of themes. Experts (two associate professor, two assistant professors) were the individuals who had expertise in thematic analysis.

Results

Data analysis revealed that national identity appeared to have two basic components (Belongingness and Sense of Nation).

Figure 1. Model of National Identity Development

Components of National identity

Belongingness

A sense of belonging to one state or country is the basic element of national identity. National identity is the proud sense of belonging to a country, nation or race. It is the element that unites people under one flag, one territory, and all the culture, history, and traditions that it represents. Thematic analysis revealed that there were two extremes of adolescents on the basis of national identity, at one extreme people were too much passionate for their country but on the other hand, some of the adolescents showed no attachment to the country. The analysis revealed that those who were not attached to the country were actually those whose love for country was conditioned with the availability of socio-economic facilities.

No country can provide us the prestige which we enjoy in Pakistan. I think if we want prestigious job then we should not go anywhere (Waqar)

The narration of the participant reflects that the participant completely understands that the prestige which he can enjoy in his own country cannot be enjoyed anywhere else. He did not talk about facilities or any monetary benefits rather he talked about pride, respect, and dignity. Furthermore, his narration reflects his belief that a job is not a problem, job can be found anywhere but the actual desired thing is prestige. Therefore he emphasizes on the point that a prestigious job is only possible in Pakistan. Here it reflects that belongingness to one's country further determines career goals and ultimately career-related identity.

I love my country and I think moving abroad is not a sensible decision. Everything is possible in Pakistan but it requires effort and those who do not want to put their effort, they move to other countries (Waqar)

The account of participants reflect that he is deeply in love with his country. His level of belongingness with the country is so strong that thoughts of leaving the country is nonsense for him. His narration reflects that he is having belief in efforts and he thinks that only those leave the country who are not willing to work hard, otherwise for a hard-working people do not leave their country.

We can live in Pakistan with full freedom. In any other country, we cannot live freely and we will always be rated as a second class citizen (Amna)

The narration above reflects that freedom is only possible in one's own country. Use of the word "second class" reflects that she is concerned about her dignity, which can be safeguard in our country of origin (i.e., Pakistan). She feels that country gives self-respect and pride.

I think we should develop our career in Pakistan as in this way we can put our efforts for the progress of our country (Amna)

I feel if I will get an opportunity to acquire a good job in any other country. I will forgo that option. We are because of this country and this country has done a lot for us, so now it is our turn to contribute to its development (Iqra)

A deep sense of belongingness reflects through the narrations of participants. It appears that they not only feel an attachment to their country but they also experience a sense of ownership. This sense of ownership guides them to plan their career in a way so that they can work for the betterment and development of the country. Their statements reflect their sense of responsibility which is actually the result of their belongingness.

I feel that I have a high level of patriotism and I want to contribute something in the development of my country (Adila)

Another participant reflects a high level of patriotism and mentions that her patriotism motivates her to do something for the development of the country.

Conditions of our country are not good but leaving the country should not be an option. Whatever the conditions of the country are, I love my country (Sara)

An emotional blend of narration reflects that participant has the realization that the conditions of her country are not good because of many social and economic problems. These socio-economic problems do not appear to affect her love for the country. She seems to love her country unconditionally. So she does not appear to support leaving one's own country for economic benefits.

I love my country and I am very hopeful about its future (Sana)

The sense of love and level of attachment is reflected through the narration given above. Her love for the country seems to make her hopeful about the future of country in terms of socioeconomic conditions.

I love my country and my all desires will be fulfilled as I am a hardworking person (Sahil)

Sahil loves his country and he is having a strong belief in his talent and he thinks that fulfillment of wishes is dependent upon one's efforts. It gives the impression that a hard-working person does not worry about the socioeconomic conditions of his/her country.

I love my country and I can do anything for my country (Zain)

The level of dedication appears through the above statement. Claim of doing everything for the country shows the depth of love for his country.

I think my desires cannot be completely fulfilled. If I will get a chance to leave the country, then I will leave it. I will enjoy more in any other country as in Pakistan, there is no freedom rather a lot of restrictions are imposed on us (Haya)

Haya's narrative reflects that her level of belongingness with the country is very weak. It appears that she does not like restrictions and she wants to have freedom in her life. She perceives that the conditions of Pakistan do not allow her to enjoy freedom. Therefore she thinks that leaving the country is the best-suited option for her.

Sense of a Nation

It is the sense of a nation as a cohesive whole, as represented by distinctive traditions, culture, language and politics.

I love my country and I love the people of this country and I want to do something for my nation (Nimra)

The sense of a nation reflects that a sense of national identity is so strong that she loves her country and loves the people of the country. It is basically an expression of attachment and a sense of ownership for the country and for the nation both.

I know we are having a lot of problems but we as a nation can solve our problems. We need to work together. We are a unit (Adila)

A deep sense of nation with the blend of maturity is reflected through the account of Adila. She appears to have a sense of cohesiveness. She has the realization that country is facing many problems, but the unity of the nation will resolve these problems. It appears that the unity of nation makes people hopeful regarding their future as a citizen.

Factors influencing National Identity

National identity is not an inborn trait and it is essentially socially constructed (Anderson, 1991). The study has revealed various factors which influence the national identity of adolescents.

Parents

As national identity is a socially constructed phenomenon and at this stage of life the most important role is played by parents.

Papa says that Pakistan is a good country and economic conditions of Pakistan can be easily improved through industries (Ali).

The narration of participants reflects that national identity is basically constructed on the basis of the national identity of parents.

My parents are here so I don't want to leave this country. I think leaving our country is really a silly act (Ali).

My parents are living here and I cannot think about leaving this country. I do not know how people leave their country and leave their parents, family and other people (Zain).

Belongingness with the country is because of belongingness with the parents. The country is identified with the presence of parents there. It seems that love for country and love for parents are overlapped.

My papa says if a country will demand our lives, we can sacrifice for our country. I think we should stand with our country at any cost (Sara).

Sara's statement reflects that her level of patriotism is actually influenced by his father. Ready to sacrifice life for the sake of the country is the peak of love for the country. This statement is actually the deep emotional attachment of her father with the country and this attachment is transferred into Sara.

I love my country...Papa says our problem is just a burden of loan otherwise we are having all the facilities in Pakistan (Sana).

It seems that Sana's emotion of love is influenced by the cognitive structuring by her father about the value of her country

Media

Media appears to play a significant role in the national identity of adolescents.

Whenever I listen to any national song on TV and radio, it makes me more motivated to do something for our country (Nimra).

News about the bravery and courage of Pakistani souldiers arouses positive emotions for my country (Zain).

Dramas about the scarifices of Muslims on 14th august 1947, reminds me that my country is so important for me as it is a result of my forefathers efforts (Mavra).

The account of the participant reflects that media is a source of motivation to do something for the country. She highlights the importance of national songs, news, dramas.

When I read or listen about the corruption and injustice in Pakistani organizations then I really want to leave this country (Salaar).

I have seen a lot of videos on youtube about the living conditions of eurpean countries and their lifestyles reflect that they are prosperous. But when I look at living style of Pakistani people then I feel that in next 1000 years our life style cannot be improved (Haya).

Statement of participants reflect that media is playing role in distorting the national identity of adolescents. Due to the media adolescents can compare the living conditions across countries easily and therefore they experience more pessimism due to the huge difference in living conditions.

Economic Conditions

Analysis of data reveals that socio-economic conditions of the country plays a significant role in the national identity of adolescents.

I think there are restricted opportunities in Pakistan so if a person wants to progress then he must go out of this country (Salaar).

Pakistani population is suffering from poverty and I think there living conditions are going to be more worse in next coming years (Haya).

I think facilities and living standard is very important. Here socioeconomic conditions do not allow us to live a comfortable life. So if Pakistan is not proving good living conditions, then moving to any other country is not a bad idea (Ahad)

Participants describe their national identity by evaluating the socioeconomic conditions of Pakistan. Currently, Pakistan is struggling with a lot of issues like, inflation, unemployment, and poverty etc. Socioeconomic conditions of Pakistan appears to be a major reason behind the troubled national identity of adolescents. Narrations of participants reflect that economic conditions of Pakistan have made them them hopeless. It appears that at this stage belongingness and love for country is conditioned with the services and opportunities provided by the country and government.

Our country is blessed with talent and resources and I hope one day it will be one of the developed countries (Mavra).

On the other had, Mavra seems to be hopeful. Her narration reflects that she is not unaware of socio-economic scenario but she has a firm belief that Pakistan is blessed with talented people and facilities and these things are the prerequisite for any country to progress.

Peer

Peer group also plays a significant role in the confusion/formation of national identity. Peers appear to share knowledge and information that weakens the belongingness of adolescents with the country.

I think, I cannot earn sufficient money in Pakistan. My friends tell me stories about their cousins who are living luxurious lives in other countries. Why should I waste my life here. If io will get any opportunity then I will definatly prefer to leave the country and will enjoy my life (Salaar).

Most of my friends aspire to live in any european country (Ahmad).

The narration above reflects that peers do not directly influence the national identity of adolescents rather their company indirectly influences their national identity. Listening to the success stories of those who left Pakistan had strong impressions on Salaar's national identity. It seems that peers at this stage fascinate the adolescents and their views have a strong impact on their national identity.

Discussion

Thematic analysis revealed that national identity comprised of two components(belongingness and sense of nation). National identity is a biproduct of commonalities in the lives of citizens for instance, [language](#), history, living styles. People integrate national identity into their self identities gradually by having beliefs, values, assumptions, and expectations which are associated with one's national identity (Lazzlo, 2013). National identity can is a collective product (Lee, 2012). Process of socialization helps in the transmission of values, beliefs and expectation in the individuals that help in the development of their sense of nation (Smith, 1991). According to Lee (2012), level and nature of national identity is dependent upon the level of socialization .

The current study revealed that various factors influenced the national identity of individuals. The analysis revealed that parents' media, peer and socioeconomic conditions of the country are playing a significant role in the national identity. National identity had never been qualitatively explored previously so this is the uniqueness of our study. A significant role appeared to be played by the socioeconomic conditions of the country. Currently, Pakistan is struggling for its survival. People are facing challenges like, poverty etc.. Poverty is the result of economic, social, and political processes that interact with and reinforce each other in ways that can accentuate the state of deprivation in which poor people live. In the current scenario, adolescents' national identity appeared to become weaker. They are hopeless because they are observing the problems in their country so they find it a better option to think about leaving the country.

Parents play a significant positive role in national identity development. Parents are well familir with the struggle of forefathers and they tell the positive avenues to their children, as a result, it positively influences the national identity of adolescents. All the factors are playing dual role, in some cases these factors are strengthening the national identity and in some cases, these factors are distorting the national identity. Influence of these factors are context and content-specific. For instance media through national songs develops belongingness and a sense of nation but on the other hand, media reflecting injustice, corruption, poverty in Pakistan is playing the opposite role.

Gender differences are found in the belongingness and sense of nation. Girls appeared to have a sense of nation because they reported being more emotional about their country which makes girls more concerned about their nation. Boys appeared to have belongingness with the country but they did not appear to be concerned with the problems of the nation rather most of the boys reported their intention of leaving the country literature also highlights differences in the identity development of girls and boys. The level of identity foreclosure is higher among boys as compared to girls (Archer, 1989). A high level of foreclosure might be the reason behind the less belongingness with the country among boys. Currently, Pakistan is facing a lot of economical and political problems and most of the people are not satisfied with the facilities and resources available in the country. Boys are considered as the bread winners of the society and they are getting impression from their families, media and peers that their bight future is not possible in Pakistan, so they thinkto leave their country. While girls are not worried about jobs and earnings in future, therefore they showed belongingness with the country.

Recommendation and Implications

The current study helped in exploring a very important construct. It is recommended that future quantitative studies should be conducted on the basis of the results of this qualitative work. It would be a good contribution if the national identity scale would be developed especially for the Pakistani population. It highlighted the

important role of media, parents, peers, and teachers. The media should devise certain strategies, so that the national identity of adolescents could be properly developed.

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